

Because it was difficult to time the heat treatment during meiotic or booting stage, only two varieties gave sufficient data over all dates of the experiment. The average percentage of filled grains for panicles flowering on different dates is shown in the figure. Data from both high temperature treatments were combined. At least three panicles were used for each average. Those flowering after the temperature treatment are on the negative side of 0 in the figure (treated before flowering) and those flowering before the treatment are on the positive side.

IET4568 was moderately tolerant in a previous study, but was relatively susceptible in this study. The two most susceptible stages were anthesis and about 10 d before anthesis, which confirms previous results. IR2006-P12-12-2-2 was highly tolerant of high temperature at anthesis in previous studies. In this study, it was tolerant at anthesis and meiotic stages.

In control treatments, IET4568 had an average fertility of 74% and IR2006 had an average of 92%, confirming earlier studies showing that heat-tolerant varieties have higher fertility even under control conditions. It is not clear if the toler-

Average filled spikelets percentage for panicles flowering on different days in relation to a high temperature treatment. The 5 d treatment of 35/27°C was given on days -2 to 2, and is shown by the shaded bar.

ance mechanism is the same for both stages. It may be that the high anther dehiscence of IR2006 allows it to overcome the high temperature damage caused during the meiotic stage, as

well as at anthesis. This line should be an excellent donor of high temperature tolerance for breeding programs for semi-arid countries where temperature is high during flowering. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

COLD TOLERANCE

Assessment of cold tolerance of Korean rice varieties by chlorophyll fluorescence analysis

Y. D. Rho, Rice Production Department, Crop Experiment Station, Office of Rural Development, Suweon, Korea; and J. M. Wilson, School of Plant Biology, University College of North Wales, Bangor, Gwynedd LL57 2UW, UK

Visual assessment of cold injury based on chlorosis, browning, leaf rolling, and necrosis of rice leaves is subjective and time-consuming, especially because some of the symptoms appear only after prolonged cold or when temperatures rise. We evaluated the potential of chlorophyll fluorescence analysis for quantitative assessment of cold damage because it is

quick and can detect damage before visual symptoms appear.

When a leaf is illuminated, the chlorophyll in the membranes of the chloroplasts emits a red fluorescence of which a part, the variable chlorophyll fluorescence, is responsive to photosystem II activity. Any stress such as cold, frost, drought, or pollutants that affects photosynthetic metabolism is likely to change the fluorescence. We measured fluorescence with a plant productivity fluorimeter. The machine uses a probe that is placed on the adaxial surface of the leaf to provide the illumination and collect the fluorescent light.

In the experiment, we chilled 11 Korean rices with a range of chill sensitivity for 8 d at 10°C, 85% relative humidity, under a 12-h day cycle at 30,000 lux. The

plants were 60 d old and were grown in the glasshouse in Jul and Aug. For each variety, 5 flag leaves were randomly selected and 3 readings made at the leaf base, middle, and tip. The values are the mean of 15 readings. Fluorescence measurements were made after 5 h dark acclimation at 27°C for the controls and at 10°C for the chilled plants.

Changes in fluorescence emission occurred during the first 3 s after illuminating a dark-adapted leaf (Fig. 1). Light caused the chlorophyll fluorescence to rise immediately to 0 and this initial level is termed F_0 . Fluorescence slowly increased to a peak F_{max} , which is attained at p . For quantifying cold injury, the rate of rise of variable chlorophyll fluorescence (F_R) is the most important parameter and can be calculated by drawing a straight line to

the linear part of the fluorescence rise as indicated by the dashed line in Figure 1. Figure 1 also shows that both the rate of F_R and maximum fluorescence yield (F_{var}) declined after 8 d chilling at 10°C in the varieties Pungsan-byeo, Taebaeg-byeo, and Hanganchal-byeo.

Figure 2 compares the changes in chlorophyll fluorescence (as a percentage of the control at 27°C) after 8 d chilling at 10°C with the visual estimation of cold damage made on a 1 to 9 scale at the end of chilling. The japonica varieties Samnam-byeo (10) and Sangpung-byeo (11) were the most cold tolerant. Their fluorescence increased 23-34% during chilling. In contrast, indica/japonica varieties Taebaeg-byeo (1), Milyang 77 (9), Hanganchal-byeo (6), and Chupung-byeo (4) were the most susceptible to cold and F_R decreased 77, 89, 95, and 98% compared to the controls. The more cold-tolerant indica/japonica varieties tested had smaller decreases in chlorophyll fluorescence, which agreed with visual observations of injury (Fig. 2).

The increases in fluorescence of the more cold tolerant varieties Milyang 23 (7), Baegyung-byeo (8), Samnam-byeo (10), and Sangpung-byeo (11) after chilling are unusual and have not been reported. The increases can be interpreted as indicating acclimation or hardening to low temperatures and may be the result of increased chlorophyll content of the leaves at 10°C.

The agreement between changes in fluorescence and visual symptoms of cold injury indicates that chlorophyll fluorescence analysis could help plant breeders quickly screen large numbers of plants for cold tolerance. It is a sensitive, rapid, reproducible, nondestructive, and inexpensive technique.

Further evaluation of the chlorophyll fluorescence technique is needed in relation to plant development stage, sensitivity to other environmental factors, and different temperature treatments. The ability to detect cold damage to the thylakoid membranes by chlorophyll fluorescence analysis should not only be useful to plant breeders but also provide plant physiologists with insight into the causes and mechanisms of cold injury and hardening. □

1. Changes in the chlorophyll fluorescence kinetics of rice leaves of 3 varieties after 8 d chilling at 10°C, 85% relative humidity. The results are the mean measurements of 15 replications.

2. Changes in the rate of rise of variable fluorescence (F_R) of the leaves of 11 rice varieties (expressed as a percentage of the control at 27°C) after 8 d chilling at 10°C, 85% relative humidity compared with a visual assessment of injury on a 1 to 9 scale. 1) Taebaeg-byeo (I/J), 2) Chungchung-byeo (I/J), 3) Pungsan-byeo (I/J), 4) Chupung-byeo (I/J), 5) Milyang 23 (I/J), 6) Hanganchalbyeo (I/J), 7) Manseog-byeo (I/J), 8) Baeuang-byeo (I/J), 9) Milyang 77 (I/J), 10) Samnam-byeo (J), 11) Sangpung-byeo (J). I or J indicates whether variety is an indica or japonica or a cross between the 2.

A modified technique of screening for cold tolerance in rice

R. N. Kaw and G. S. Khush, IRRI

At IRRI, we measure cold tolerance by the degree of discoloration of 10-d-old

seedlings treated with 12°C water for 10 d. Although this screening method quickly discriminates between cultivars that remain green and those that turn yellow and die, it does not allow breeding materials to be ranked in relative order of hardiness, nor does it consider variations